

**PHYTOCENOSSES OF SPECIES BELONGING TO THE FAMILY CYPERACEAE
JUSS., NOM. CONS. DISTRIBUTED IN THE NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC
FLORA**

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Abstract: *Plants belonging to the Cyperaceae Juss., nom. cons. family are one of the components of the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and mainly spread in wetlands. They are most common in mountainous areas, especially in lakes located on the Batabat plateau and on the banks of the Araz River. Many species of the Cyperaceae Juss., nom. cons. family are directly dependent on the annual nominal change in the water level in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. Plants of the Cyperaceae Juss., nom. cons. family are more common in swamps or places where the water level changes frequently. Plants with high water requirements are of great importance in the protection of the ecosystem, as well as nature. Species of the Cyperaceae Juss., nom. cons. family enrich the vegetation of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, creating various phytocenoses and formations. Representatives of the family distinguish by their wide ecological groups and morphological diversity. Considering that the species are both poisonous and non-poisonous, as well as honey-producing plants, we see that they are an important structural component in the vegetation.*

Keywords: *phytocenos 1, formation 2, species 3, family 4, ecosystem 5.*

Резюме: *Растения семейства Cyperaceae Juss., ном. конс. являются одним из компонентов флоры Нахчыванской Автономной Республики и распространены преимущественно в заболоченных местах. Наиболее часто они встречаются в горных районах, особенно в озерах, расположенных на Батабатском плато и на берегах реки Араз. Многие виды семейства Cyperaceae Juss., ном. конс. напрямую зависят от ежегодного номинального изменения уровня воды на территории Нахчыванской Автономной Республики. Растения семейства Cyperaceae Juss., ном. конс. чаще встречаются в болотах или местах с частыми изменениями уровня воды. Растения с высокими водопотребностями имеют большое значение для охраны экосистемы, а также природы. Виды семейства Cyperaceae Juss., ном. конс. обогащают растительность Нахчыванской Автономной Республики, создавая различные фитоценозы и формации. Представители этого семейства отличаются широкими экологическими группами и морфологическим разнообразием. Учитывая, что среди видов встречаются как ядовитые, так и неядовитые растения, а также медоносные, мы видим, что они являются важной структурной составляющей растительности.*

INTRODUCTION

Representatives of the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family also differ in their reaction to anthropogenic factors. Irrigation canals and artificial ponds increase the spread of *Cyperus* and *Schoenoplectus* species. The use of various chemicals and herbicides during the cleaning of agricultural crops leads to the disappearance of many species of the *Carex* genus. The phytomelodic properties of the species of the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family predominate. These species are

an important flora element in coastal stabilization, erosion prevention, and restoration of wetland ecosystems.

Species belonging to the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family participate in the formation and enrichment of various types of phytocenoses in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. These phytocenoses have a unique ecological and economic significance. Studying the possibilities of using phytocenoses is of great importance in terms of evaluating these plants as a natural resource.

Cyperaceae Juss., nom. cons. The species of the genus form the following phytocenoses in the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic:

- Grassland and meadow-shrubby
- Reedbeds and reed-like phytocenoses
- Mountain slopes and stony soil phytocenoses
- Phytocenoses of rivers and floodplains
- Phytocenoses of river valleys and humid areas
- Endemic and relict phytocenoses

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

Classical botanical, floristic, systematic, archaeological, ecological and statistical methods were also used in the processing of the materials [16, 17]. Phenological observations were carried out based on I.N. Beideman [18].

The studies were carried out in 2024-2025 based on generally accepted geobotanical methods and had a precise route and semi-stationary character. Floristic and methodological expeditions were carried out in the ecological areas of the Sadarak, Sharur, Kangarli, Shahbuz, Julfa and Ordubad administrative districts of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, both along the Araz River, as well as in the high and middle mountainous areas where the species of the family are widespread.

During the research, I used the Herbarium Fund of the Institute of Bioresources of Nakhchivan State University, the Herbarium Fund of the Department of Biology of Nakhchivan State University, the literature information in the Scientific Library of Nakhchivan State University, classical and modern literature on the flora of Azerbaijan, including Nakhchivan, and the family *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS OF THE RESEARCH

Many species of the family *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. **participate in the formation of grass meadow and meadow-shrub** phytocenoses in the middle and high mountains of Nakhchivan. Species of the genus *Carex* L. dominate in this phytocenosis. *Carex acutiformis*, *Carex diandra*, *Carex disticha*, etc. species participate in the prevention of soil erosion and soil formation.

These phytocenoses are considered important due to the following properties:

- As hayfields and limited pastures in early spring
- Restoration of soil cover and regulation of water regime
- Protection of biodiversity and ensuring ecological stability
- Landscape ecology and recreational purposes

Since excessive grazing in meadows leads to degradation of phytocenoses, use norms should be determined on a scientific basis.

Reed beds and reed-like phytocenoses – Reed beds are considered plant communities formed in the coastal zones of water bodies and wetlands, dominated mainly by species such as *Bolboschoenus martimus*, partly *Cyperus longus*.

These phytocenoses are considered important due to the following characteristics:

- Source of raw materials for technical purposes (wicker products, household items, roofing)
- Strengthening coastal zones and combating erosion
- Improving the ecological condition of water bodies and reducing pollution
- Formation of a shelter and food base for birds and other aquatic fauna

During the sustainable use of reed beds, the harvesting intensity should be regulated, and the self-recovery capacity of the phytocenoses should be taken into account.

Mountain slopes and stony soil phytocenoses - many species of the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family create special formation associations on skeletal and stony soils. The plants included in these phytocenoses are mainly low-growing, drought-resistant.

Carex melanostachya Bieb. ex Willd., *Koberesia macrolepis* Meinsh., *Carex huetiana* Boiss., *Carex aterrima* Hoppe = *C. a. subsp. medwedewii* (Leskov) Egor., *Carex caryophyllea* Latourr., etc. species form the basis of this phytocenose. These phytocenoses are observed in the subalpine and alpine zones.

Phytocenoses of river and floodplains - Some species of the family are widespread on forest edges, in thickets. In these areas they create shade-loving phytocenoses. The composition of these phytocenoses mainly consists of *Carex acuta* L. (*C. dichroandra* V.Krecz.), *Carex hordeistichos* Vill., *Carex distans* L. etc. species. These species increase the diversity of the substratum, maintain normal soil moisture, and contribute to the protection of forest ecosystems.

River valleys and wetlands - species of the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family constitute almost the basis of the Nakhchivan flora.

Nakhchivan shay, Jahri chay, Paraghachay, etc. form the basis of the phytomass of the banks of other shays

Carex riparia Cart. spreading phytocenosis

The species included in the phytocenosis develop better in river valleys, on moist and humid soils. These plants mainly spread together with low-growing grasses, creating harmony within the ecosystem.

The phytocenosis of river valleys and humid areas is composed of *Cyperus longus*, *Bolboschoenus maritimus*, *Carex riparia* Curt., *Carex acutiformis* Ehrh., *Carex vesicaria* L., *Schoenus nigricans* L., etc. These plants grow on river banks and carry out biological filtration of water through their roots.

These phytocenoses are considered important due to the following features:

- soil consolidation and prevention of coastal erosion
- biological protection of irrigation systems
- creation of ecological buffer zones in agroecosystems

Small local phytocenoses formed by endemic and relict species - some relict and endemic species of the *Cyperaceae* Juss., nom. cons. family form local formation associations in special microhabitats - rock outcrops, high mountain and subalpine meadows.

Carex caryophyllea Latourr., *Carex supina* Willd. ex Wahlenb., *Carex tristis* Bieb. are found in small local phytocenoses formed by endemic and relict species. The number of species in these associations is very small. Despite this, they have ecological and genetic characteristics.

These phytocenoses are considered important due to the following features:

- Soil consolidation and prevention of coastal erosion
- Assessment of resource potential
- Monitoring of rare and limited distribution species
- Study of the possibilities of introduction and artificial propagation

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